

3D Printing in the Humanities – Use Cases and Best Practice

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Summary

This section is a summary of the main points in the guide. Some will make more sense after you've read the guide, but they provide a useful starting point for anyone considering using a 3D printer.

To 3D print something, you need an STL file that represents it. STL is a file format for 3D models. Once you have your model, load it into [Cura](#) and decide on how you want to print it (warning: there are lots of permutations in 3D printing!). The key settings to adjust depending on your use case are:

- **Infill density:** use a high density for greater weight and strength, though material usage and print time will increase.
- **Profile thickness:** use a smaller setting for a finer surface texture, though this will greatly increase print time.

- **Scale:** upscaling will cause a drop in resolution, similar to upscaling an image. Downscaling will also cause a drop in resolution if the model has features that are at the detail limit, i.e. the minimum profile thickness set by the printer hardware.
- **Support:** use PVA (glue) support if available, as this can be dissolved in water after printing. Breakaway PLA support can be used in easy-to-reach areas. Experiment with changing support angles to reduce volume of support used.
- **Adhesion:** use a skirt where no support from the base plate is required as the model will definitely not move during printing. Otherwise, use a brim as your default. If you have an unstable and awkward shape, use a raft so the model doesn't fall over during printing.

Typical problems to consider:

- **Stringing, blemishes and Z-seam:** These are errors on the model itself. They tend to occur where filament is under the wrong pressure coming out of the nozzle so it either comes out too quickly or gets blocked. Stringing occurs when the nozzle becomes blocked while the head is moving, resulting in a 'string' of material missing from a single layer. Blemishes are more general and occur when the nozzle becomes clogged and produces blotches of filament. Z-seam is when the nozzle prints a burst of filament at the start of each layer in the same place, causing a vertical blemish. These can be fixed by lowering print head speed and temperature, or by changing your printer hardware.
- **Glue clogs in internal cavities:** PVA support can get stuck in hard-to-reach cavities since water access is needed for it to dissolve. Consider running water over the model for a length of time or using warmer water.
- **Delamination:** Layers separate from each other because of a lack of support, causing strings of filament to be deposited everywhere. Use more supports by changing the support angle setting.
- **Lack of strength:** use one of the infill patterns optimised for strength (in Custom settings), such as Gyroid or Cubic.

Use cases for 3D printing can include printing musical instruments, historical artifacts, household objects and engineering parts (or at least those are the ones we've thought of at the time of writing!). It can also reproduce objects when combined with photogrammetry (or a similar 3D scanning process), which you can do with your phone camera and free online software.

Fidelity. The true size of an object is often impossible to produce with 3D printing, so some of the object's impact is taken away when it is reproduced. The grandeur and magnificence of a statue is one such example. The weight is also difficult to reproduce, since PLA plastic (which is typically used for printing) is light. This can be overcome by using metal, stone or glass filaments, though these are often very expensive. However, for applications where geometry is the most important factor, 3D printing excels, since its flexibility allows it to produce a huge range of different shapes. For example, you can produce woodwind instruments that work well very easily with a free model from the internet.

3D printing is good at producing small, functional parts where a very smooth surface texture is not especially important. It can produce certain internal features and complex structures that are impossible or impractical with conventional manufacturing (because it prints from bottom to the top). However, for applications where you need to print simple parts in bulk, 3D printing is not the best option because of the high print times and material costs. If this is what you need to do, try the EDMC design workshops instead.

General printing process for Ultimaker Cura

This is a general outline of the printing process, from a 3D model to a physical object. For a more detailed explanation of the UI, see the Ultimaker Cura manual created by Luke Aspland, found on the [Digital Humanities Sharepoint](#).

- 1 – **Load in your model** so it appears on the grey base plate.
- 2 – **Select print settings**, including Profiles, Infill, Support, and Adhesion. For more control over these parameters choose 'Custom'.
- 3 – **Select materials**. There will be one material for each of the two extruders. Select which material will be the 'Support' and which will be the material used for the model itself. If there are no materials loaded, you will need to mount the spools into the 3D printer.
- 4 – **Edit the position and orientation** of the model. You can also scale its size and add more mirrored objects. Remember to keep the model within the bounding box.
- 5 – **Slice** the model.
- 6 – Select '**Preview**' to check the model will print correctly, and check you are happy with the print time, weight and cost.
- 7 – **Print** the model. Select the 'Monitor' tab to see information about the print.

Profiles

Profile settings for the headers installed on the Ultimaker S5 printer in the Digital Humanities Hub vary from 0.6mm to 4mm. This controls the thickness of the layers of material, as the 3D printer operates by placing thin slices of material on top of one another.

Generally, **thicker** profiles mean:

- **Faster** print time.
- **Coarser** surface finish.
- **Less detail** in surface features.
- **Thin features may be impossible**, such as walls and corners, and smooth round features.
- Part **tolerances** will be much greater.

For more information, see:

<https://www.hubs.com/knowledge-base/impact-layer-height-3d-print/>

Table 1 - Print time, recommended use cases, and surface finish for different printer profile settings

Layer thickness (mm)	0.06	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.3	0.4
Approximate increase on print time compared to 0.3mm*	5.5x	3.5x	2.5x	1.5x	1x	N/A
Suitable for	Visual	Visual, Engineering	Visual, Engineering	Draft	Draft	Coarse drafts
Recommended use cases	Fine reproduction of historical objects, creating ornaments, or creating operational engineering prototypes	Rough reproduction of larger historical objects, creating ornaments, or creating operational engineering prototypes with larger tolerances	Creating operational engineering prototypes with much larger tolerances	Creating initial rough drafts of objects	Creating initial rough drafts of objects	Checking printing occurs without errors, creating very rough drafts
Surface finish quality	Smooth to the touch, though ridges still apparent to naked eye	Slightly ridged texture	Slightly ridged texture	Coarse texture	Coarse texture	Very coarse texture

* for Cuneiform tablet model

Infill

Increasing infill proportion will increase strength, print time, and weight. This is because the rate of deposition of material is limited by the hardware. Mass and print time are directly correlated to infill density used:

Figure 1 - Mass of 3D models vs. infill density for cuneiform tablet example

Figure 2 – Print time of 3D models vs. infill density for cuneiform tablet example

Infill proportion is related to mass by changing the size of the gaps within the internal lattice structure. 0% infill will give a completely hollow structure, while increasing the infill will reduce the sizes of the internal cavities. For more information, see <https://www.tianseoffice.com/blog/how-to-use-infill-percentage-and-pattern-enhance-strength-save-material/>

Figure 3 - Internal structures at different infill percentages

Infill proportion (%)	Description
<20	<p>Best for draft or display items, as the structure will not have much strength or stability. The surface will also be slightly rougher (see Figure 4Figure 1). If there are wide elevated flat parts on the model, using this infill value may cause printer errors, as the material may not be adequately supported over the empty spaces in the infill lattice. See 5% infill on Figure 3 for an illustration.</p> <p>I printed a Julius Caesar statuette at 10% infill, and a Cuneiform tablet at 20% without any problems. I would recommend following the program's default setting of 20% from my experience, unless there's a good reason not to.</p>
20-50	<p>This infill density is a good middle ground between draft and functional prototypes of 3D printed objects.</p>
50-100	<p>Best for functional prototypes and uses where smooth surface finish is critical. This infill can be combined with a strong infill pattern, such as cubic, to give good isotropic strength properties to the model.</p>

Surface finish depends on infill density. A denser infill will increase the support for the surface as it is printing, so layers will be less likely to move immediately after being extruded. See Figure 4 for the increase in roughness with lower infill. Even so, profile thickness will influence the surface roughness much more, as the difference over the 0.6 to 3mm range is orders of magnitude higher than the surface roughness values below. Note the difference between

different infill patterns; grid and concentric patterns, which use slightly more material than the lines pattern, are also rougher.

Table 2

Density	Infill Pattern	Printing time (Minutes)	Surface Roughness (Ra-μm)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
40%	Lines	72	15.8	20.60
40%	Grid	71	16.15	19.10
40%	Concentric	71	21.85	18.80
60%	Lines	82	5.25	26.10
60%	Grid	82	7.1	24.60
60%	Concentric	80	16.7	24.00

Figure 4 – Table from <https://www.ijedr.org/papers/IJEDR1703083.pdf>

Scale

The size of the model you are printing will impact the **amount of material used, print time and surface resolution**. When printing a large model, try not to simply upscale a smaller model, as this will reduce the resolution. Also, be aware that printing a smaller model will cause some detail to be lost, due to the finite layer thickness of the prints. As you can see in Figure 5 (right) on this small 40mm high model, the facial features are almost completely lost, because the printer was incapable of printing such small surface features. A similar effect would occur if you upscaled the model before printing.

Figure 5 - Amplified image of Julius Caesar model's facial features

For more information, see:

<https://support.shapeways.com/hc/en-us/articles/360023732334-Design-tips-for-shrinking-and-enlarging-models-to-scale>

Figure 6 - Original resolution of model nodes, left, and downsampled and upscaled 4x model, right

As you can see in Figure 6 (above), **downscaling and upscaling** a model that is at the detail limit (where the distance between nodes is equal to the minimum resolution of the printer) will cause a corresponding **drop in quality**, which is seen as flat surfaces and sharp edges on a 3D printed model. There are corresponding problems with printing very thin edges and extrusions on smaller models, as there is a minimum profile thickness on the printer.

Support

Support angle gives the **minimum angle** (measured from the horizontal) that an overhang must be for the program to generate a support strut for it. This will be dependent on how viscous the material being used is. Also, if you are using a slower print speed, the support requirement is greater. See for more details:

<https://all3dp.com/2/3d-printing-supports-guide-all-you-need-to-know/>

You can use either **PLA** or **glue** supports for overhangs in your model. PLA supports can be removed after the print simply by snapping away, or if necessary with a modelling knife. Cura is supposed to generate the PLA support with only a small number of contact points to facilitate this, though for complex structures with lots of curves and corners (Figure 7, left) we found that it can generate too many (such that for Figure 7 we observed the model with supports looked like Julius Caesar hugging a skyscraper!). Each of these contact points bonds the support to the structure, so a small amount of support material is left on the model. This can lead to discolouration and an uneven surface when the supports are removed (Figure 7, right). This is bad for models where surface finish is important.

Figure 7 - Julius Caesar model with PLA supports (left), and with supports removed (right)

Figure 7, left, is an example of **excessive supports** being used. This should be avoided because it causes **waste** and **increases print times**. We found that the result of the software algorithm should not be taken at face value; here, the supports were sufficient to ensure the model was printed correctly, but left many black patches that need to be removed meticulously with a knife. If this model was used for teaching or research purposes, this added work would greatly reduce interest in 3D printing for tactile understanding of the object, because of the reduced aesthetic quality. This illustrates the importance of visual appearance, even for a small figurine that is nothing like the original statue, for potential users of 3D printing.

Unlike PLA supports, glue (PVA) supports must be generated as **vertical columns**. When using PVA supports we found that there is a tendency for Cura to create far more supports than it needs at any overhang angle less than 80°. PVA supports are water soluble, so are far easier to remove, and do not leave marks on the surface after removal, unlike bonded PLA supports (see Figure 8, below).

Figure 8 (left) - PLA-supported model after support removal

Figure 9 (right) - Cuneiform tablet with crevices circled

When designing supports, another thing to consider is removal of **hard-to-reach** supports. In Figure 9 (above), you can see crevices on the Cuneiform tablet model, where any support material would be very difficult to remove. For PVA glue supports, this is not a problem, because the glue will naturally dissolve in contact with water. However, for PLA, **access** must be allowed for a knife, or the supports will not be removable.

Adhesion

Adhesion to the base plate is vital for any print, as it keeps the structure rigid and upright while printing. This can be in the form of either a brim, skirt or raft support. For more details, see <https://www.simplify3d.com/support/articles/rafts-skirts-and-brims/>.

Brims (see Figure 10, below) are a single flat layer of material printed around the base of the model. Due to the high build plate temperature (typically 60°C) this bonds to the plate and can be peeled off afterwards with a knife. You can choose either extruder's material for any support type, but I recommend the build material (PLA in my case) as it can be snapped off easily after printing.

Figure 10 - An example of a brim support

Brim

s provide moderate adhesion, as they are attached to your model. They help prevent warping (where plastic contracts while cooling down) and give some extra stability to models with a small footprint. Brims are fast, use only a small amount of filament, and are the first type of support you should try for a given model.

Figure 11 - an example of a skirt support

Skirts (see Figure 11, above) are used where there is no adhesion requirement between the model and the plate, and serve as a way to ensure filament runs smoothly from the extruder. They use even less material than brims, but do not contribute to the stability of the model during printing.

Raft supports (see Figure 12, below) are much bulkier, and provide a platform on which your model is printed. The raft can be peeled off after printing in a similar way to the brim. They bond the model more strongly than a brim, though they use more material and take much longer to print. Raft supports should be used for awkward or unstable shapes that pose a serious risk of falling during printing.

Figure 12 – an example of a raft support

Use Cases

3D printing can be used for:

- Accurately **reproducing** historical artifacts to be touched, felt, and experimented with.
- Making end-use or prototype **engineering parts** with fine tolerances.
- Creating **ornaments**.
- Creating **drafts** of products that can be interacted with.

Case Study 1 – Bust of Julius Caesar

In this case study, three different versions of the same model were printed:

Figure 13 - Julius Caesar statue

This sculpture was made by Nicolas Coustou and unveiled in 1696 for display in the Tuileries gardens in Paris. It is made of marble, and attempts to duplicate the style of sculptors in Ancient Rome. There is fine attention to detail, in the form of the billowing cloak, outstretched arm and stately figure. However, as this sculpture was only made just over 300 years ago, its condition is much better than statues from the time period. The model can be found at <https://www.myminifactory.com/object/3d-print-julius-caesar-153996> .

When trying to 3D print a model of this sculpture, I found that supporting the arm overhang was challenging (see Figure 13, centre), as it required a large amount of material for support, which was then difficult to remove without breaking off the arm. This may be a challenge for marble sculptors too, as thin, outstretched parts are easy to break, and cannot then be reattached. Also, learning how to print this model accurately took significant time and effort,

which would also be found by sculptors. Thus, making this model illuminates the careful thought and meticulous craftsmanship that goes into making a marble statue.

However, the value in such a statue is in more than just the structure. The original sculpture is much larger than life, which conveys the strength and grandeur of Julius Caesar, as the first Roman emperor. Especially, when displayed in a museum and surrounded by people, the immensity of the statue will stand out even more. This effect is lost in a 3D printed model, as it is impractical to print at this scale. Thus, it is important to remember that much of the message that Coustou was trying to convey in this work of art is lost, as the scale can only be experienced in the original model.

The texture of the printed models also leaves much to be desired. Marble is a high-quality material: it is smooth and cold, as it reflects the ruthless determination and harsh character of the figure. This effect can probably even be experienced at a distance without touching. However, though you may be able to reproduce the colour, even at a fine profile setting the surface will be rough to the eye, and it comes across as a poor reproduction of the original.

Arguably, the smooth surface is the most important attribute of the model after feature detail, because it replicates a smooth marble statue. A nicked surface would lessen the accuracy of the model, and make feeling it much less useful.

Figure 14 - Julius Caesar models 1, 2 and 3, left to right

The first printed model (Figure 14, left) was unsupported, and as a result his arm broke off at the elbow. The layer thickness was set to 0.1mm, which led to a slightly rough surface finish. Infill density was set to 10% and the structure used a raft base. The support angle was left at the default of 60°. This was sufficient for the structure to stay intact and upright when printing, though the model feels fragile and light, because of the small infill percentage. Though the craftsmanship and skill that went into the original piece is still evident, many of the finer features are lost because of the small model size. For this reason, the model feels more like a replica of an ancient statue, with poor condition and broken parts, which I think is interesting because this wasn't at all the original intention. There is a definite possibility for using the limitations of the 3D printer in an artistic way to replicate the poor condition of very old artifacts.

The second model (Figure 14, middle) used PLA supports, and has a good surface finish apart from the black marks left on the model. When removing the supports, the baton broke off, which highlights the danger of using rigid supports around delicate surface features. The last model (Figure 14, right) used PVA (glue) supports that were water soluble, but since I set the support angle too high, at 82°, the printer had trouble with the arm and the layers did not settle properly, as shown by the rough texture. Neither of these undesired features really add value to the model, as they come across as imperfections that make the reproduction less accurate. For this reason, I would recommend very finely tuning the support angle for the PLA support, even to the nearest half a degree, to ensure a smooth texture without too much material wastage.

Case Study 2 – Akkadian Cuneiform Tablet

Here, I decided to try printing a historical object where surface finish is the most important feature. Since the tablet's original size was only 12cmx8cm, it is feasible to print to full size for the most accurate reproduction. A use case for this model (found at <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/the-map-of-the-world-tablet-caa0a4939bf64d6698fafb0d3f540096>, Figure 15, right) would be to observe, touch and feel the markings, and possibly do some more in-depth analysis of the handwriting style. The tablet is kept within the archives of the British museum (found at https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/W_1882-0714-509) as it is extremely old and fragile, so doing this analysis with the original object would be very difficult.

Figure 15 - Babylonian Map of the World tablet, left, and 3D printed reproduction, right

I was able to approximately reproduce the colour with the orange extruder. I believe this takes away some of the value compared to the original piece, because the original tablet was a dull, tarnished brown, a testament to its age. Similar to the Caesar statue, the colour and weight difference both take away from the impact of the original artifact.

My first attempt resulted in a printer error, as the two spools of material became entangled and stopped feeding into the printer. However, the incomplete version is incidentally a good way to observe the internal structure of a 3D printed model:

Figure 16 - Infill structure of incomplete Cuneiform tablet model

This can be used for teaching purposes to show how the printer works. The infill pattern can be changed to show the variation in shape and strength. I chose to use the 'Zigzag' infill here rather than the default triangular pattern, because the spaces between the supports were smaller for the same infill density, meaning the final model would be sturdier. Comparing the sides that did print correctly, both were reasonably high quality:

Figure 17 - Model 1, incomplete

Figure 18 - Model 2, complete

The inscriptions are just about legible, though there is a significant loss of quality from the original. This is surprising to me, because I chose the finest profile setting (0.06mm). If you knew the language well, you would still be able to read it, so for observation and study purposes this model is sufficient. See Figure 19 for a close-up view of the writing. Maybe this is more because the model isn't a perfect reproduction of the original.

Figure 19 - Close-up view of inscriptions

The model was printed at 20% infill, so it is much lighter than the original clay tablet. However, as you can see in Figure 17, the crevices and edges of the model were printed very accurately. The surfaces feel perfectly smooth to the touch, so approximates the original clay very closely. The tablet was originally supposed to be used as a map; not just to be looked at, but also to be felt, as it is drawn in physical grooves on the surface. The loss of quality in the surface hinders observing the map by eye, but from a tactile perspective it is almost perfect.

Case Study 3 - Harmonica

This is my first attempt at 3D printing a musical instrument. The model can be found at <https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:1168855>. The first model I printed did not slice correctly, so the holes were blocked (Figure 20, left). Furthermore, the lack of supports used caused the overhang containing the air cavity to droop (Figure 20, right), which would have seriously affected the acoustical properties anyway. This was only a rough draft, as shown by the high profile thickness. See below:

Figure 20 - Harmonica Model 1 – top view, left and bottom view, right

This example highlights the difficulty of printing internal cavities, as well as providing supports for the unique shapes found in musical instruments. I think PLA plastic would not be a practical choice for the support here, as it would be impossible to remove from any of the internal spaces of the harmonica. Furthermore, surface finish on internal cavities is extremely important, as this will dictate acoustical properties. My initial impression is that 3D printing musical instruments is much more difficult than creating aesthetic ornaments, because it takes skill and expertise to reproduce the sound correctly.

My second attempt was much more successful. I created a rudimentary pan flute of a different design that produces sound at discrete notes and of reasonably good quality. The playability was not greatly affected by the high profile thickness setting I used; though there are numerous small surface imperfections, they do not penetrate the internal cavity or create a significant change in the shape of the instrument. See below:

Figure 23 – Harmonica model 2 - Pan flute top view

Figure 22 - Close-up of pan flute hole imperfections

Figure 21 - Close-up of pan flute flat surface imperfections

Figure 22 shows the printing errors around the surface holes near the base of the pan flute. Here, the top surface tapers to an edge, so evidently there was insufficient support material for this to settle correctly after printing. Furthermore, as you can see in Figure 21, the flat surface of the flute came out very rough, with some minor dents going some way into the material. I think this presents an interesting contrast to the unique irregular shapes printed before, because it shows the limitations of the printer in producing flat, uniform objects. Here the profile thickness was 0.2mm in the interests of saving time, so a slightly better finish could have been achieved, but I think it is interesting to note the hardware limitations that led to these surface imperfections.

In addition, the PVA supports for the flute took a long time to dissolve. This is something to bear in mind when 3D printing musical instruments, as almost all of them have internal cavities- these make glue dissolution extremely time-consuming as there is limited water circulation. However, for all cases I would still recommend PVA over PLA supports, as breakaway material would be completely impossible to remove, rendering the instrument unplayable.

The model is faithful to the size of the original, as it is a handheld pan flute, so it was easy to recreate with reasonable amounts of time and material. For larger instruments, particularly string instruments, it might not be possible to recreate the size, which will have a subsequent effect on the pitch and tone of the model. Furthermore, the model would have to be strung separately, which adds to the labour of creating a 3D-printed instrument. Therefore, 3D printing is good for smaller, especially woodwind, instruments that can be printed in one piece.

Reproducing mass is critical, as it dictates the type of sound produced. In this case, I was able to increase the infill density to 100% to get it closer to the original mass; full replication may only be possible for wooden instruments. Overall, I think this print was successful as the flute plays steady notes at a loud volume, and I was able to play a tune with no prior experience.

Case Study 4 – Recorder

This is another woodwind instrument that should be playable straight after dissolving the supports. It can be found at <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/human-flute-v1-1c3c9e1e4e9440fa985ae998b7f01e51>. The exterior looks satisfying even though I used a 0.2mm profile thickness:

Figure 24 - Recorder, side view

Figure 25 - Recorder, end view with support Figure 26 - Recorder, end view after support removal

As can be seen clearly in Figure 24, stringing occurred on some layers. For more information on this effect, see:

https://core-electronics.com.au/tutorials/Ultimaker_Cura_Troubleshooting_your_Models.html#Fix

This occurs when the pressure on the extruder head is incorrect, causing irregular flow from the nozzle. I believe the print speed and print temperature default settings may have been incorrect for this print, as the blemishes occur randomly, rather than at the start of each layer. Even so, the structural integrity is unaffected, and probably the playability too as the defects are only very small. It is interesting to note that the recorder was printed on the Ultimaker S5

with the same settings as the pan flute (which was done on the S3), so there may be a hardware problem with the S5.

The texture of the model was very interesting, as there is a wood grain effect running the length of the flute (see Figure 24) that adds a certain realism and character to the model. If I were to print this model again, I would use a more suitable colour, such as dull brown, to accentuate this effect. I was just able to make it the original size, though it nearly exceeded the maximum span of the bed, so I had to print it diagonally. Again, this highlights some of the size constraints, even for high-spec 3D printers. I found out that the printable area of the bed is much smaller than the quoted area by the manufacturer, because the printer head can't reach the build plate edges. See the table below for more details:

Printer	Specified Width	Actual Width	Specified Depth	Actual Depth	Specified Height	Actual Height
MakerBot Replicator+	295	292	195	192	165	165
Ultimaker 3	197	188	215	185	200	200
LulzBot Mini	152	152*	152	152*	158	158
Dreammaker Overlord Pro Plus	125	79	125	79	280	255
New Matter MOD-t	150	145	100	95	125	125

Figure 27 - Table of actual vs. manufacture print bed dimensions from <https://www.zdnet.com/article/what-manufacturers-dont-want-you-to-know-the-truth-about-3d-printer-maximum-print-areas/>

Even so, I managed to print the flute without having to vertically angle it. This is fortunate because the printer would use a much larger amount of support material if part of the flute were far above the bed.

The most important thing to take away from this model is the difficulty of printing internal cavities. Inside the flute, next to the mouthpiece, there is a void within which PVA support was printed, where there are only two narrow slits for water to circulate through to dissolve the glue. They are so thin that when submerged, the slits can fill with an air pocket that stays in place due to water tension. This prevents the glue being dissolved, which causes an internal blockage that prevents air flow through the instrument, rendering it unplayable. For this reason, you should be especially careful printing models with difficult-to-access enclosed internal spaces, even though 3D printing is often marketed as being able to do this much better than conventional manufacturing techniques. We only managed to dislodge the glue with a knife by poking through the slit, which provided a path for hot water to flow through and dissolve the support.

If you want to 3D print some of your own instruments, try the list of ideas [here](#).

Appendix 1 - Approximating Mass with 3D printed models

This is a guide to approximating the true mass of an object with a 3D printed model.

Firstly, find out what the weight of your object is. If you are printing a model from the internet, and you cannot find the weight from the website, you can approximate it by multiplying the material density (kg/m^3) by an estimate of the volume (m^3) to find the mass (kg). Otherwise, weigh your object on a set of scales.

Next, set your profile thickness and support settings, as these will influence the mass of the print. Finer profile thickness settings tend to mean lighter prints. Infill pattern for this model made a negligible difference, so you can change this later without affecting the mass.

Figure 28 - Cuneiform tablet model

Figure 29 - Mass of 3D printed models vs. infill density for cuneiform tablet example

Mass and infill density scale approximately linearly, so using this assumption you can find the right infill density in just three steps. These are outlined below.

Taking the cuneiform tablet model (below, magenta coloured) as an example, let's say we want to replicate the mass of the original tablet, so it feels like the original. For the sake of argument, let's say this desired mass is 100 grams. Firstly, keep the infill density at the default setting of 20%:

The mass of material used can be seen beside 'Magenta PLA' in the bottom right because this is the printing material. An exploded view can be seen below.

Here the mass is 76.9g, which is too small. In this case, increase infill density to 100%, since this will give the maximum possible mass. This will allow you to see if you need to use a denser material. If the mass is too great, reduce the infill density to 5% and follow a similar process to the one described below.

MATERIAL ESTIMATION

Magenta PLA	25.27m	199.9g	€ 0.00
Natural PVA	4.30m	33.8g	€ 0.00

🕒 **13 hours 59 minutes** ⓘ

🌀 234g · 29.57m

Print over network ▾

Here, the mass of PLA is 199.9g, which is too large. Therefore, the third step is to perform a linear interpolation between the 20% and 100% masses. The formula for this is:

$$PI = 80 \left(\frac{DM - M_{20}}{M_{100} - M_{20}} \right) + 20$$

Where PI = Percentage infill (%)

DM = Desired mass (g)

M₂₀ = Mass at 20% infill (g)

M₁₀₀ = Mass at 100% infill (g)

For my example, using this formula gave me 39% percentage infill. Inputting this value using the 'Custom' infill setting gave me a mass of 97.6g after slicing, which is very close to the value of 100g that I wanted. Of course, if extra precision is required you can do some more tinkering with the infill density value.

Appendix 2 - Safety

Most 3D printing uses filament extrusion, which can cause health problems if misused. Risk factors include, but are not limited to:

- Prolonged exposure to **fumes**.
- **Contact with corrosive substances** if used to dissolve supports, e.g. caustic soda.
- **Mouth contact** with a model.
- **Burns** from contact with the extruder.

Prolonged exposure to fumes

Most 3D printers use thermoplastic extrusion, which can release harmful gases and particulates into the air. These include VOCs (Volatile Organic Compounds) and UFPs (Ultrafine Particles), both of which are nanoparticles.¹ PLA printing is less dangerous because it produces lactide, which is non-toxic.² However, special care should be taken when using non-standard filaments, such as metal and stone. There is no standard for 3D printer emissions due to the novelty of the technology,³ so it is best not to take unnecessary risks.

One way to mitigate this risk is to use ventilation. Small, windowless rooms should have ventilation installed to reduce the build-up of toxic fumes over time. This can be combined with an enclosure to prevent particulates from escaping into the room.

Contact with corrosive substances

When the drawbacks of PLA or glue supports (as mentioned above) prove insurmountable, some people opt for High-Impact Polystyrene (HIPS) supports. HIPS is a durable material that does not break down in air, and so causes less nozzle clogging. It also needs to be removed from models with caustic soda (diluted NaOH) or similar. If you do opt for this option, wear gloves and other personal protective equipment to prevent skin contact with the solvent.⁴

Mouth contact with model

This is the main concern for the musical instruments described above. While PLA is Generally Recognised As Safe (GRAS), meaning it can be used for food packaging, it releases a small

¹ Azimi, P., Zhao, D., Pouzet, C., Crain, N.E. and Stephens, B. (2016). Emissions of Ultrafine Particles and Volatile Organic Compounds from Commercially Available Desktop Three-Dimensional Printers with Multiple Filaments. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 50(3), pp.1260–1268.

² Flynt, J. (2019). 3D Printer Fumes: How bad for you are they? [online] 3D Insider. Available at: <https://3dinsider.com/3d-printer-fumes/>.

³ Acs.org. (2022). [online] Available at: <https://cen.acs.org/articles/96/i13/3-D-printer-emissions-raise.html> [Accessed 25 Apr. 2022].

⁴ www.xioneer.com. (n.d.). How Safe Are Solvents For Support Materials in FFF? – Xioneer Systems. [online] Available at: <https://www.xioneer.com/dissolving/how-safe-are-solvents-for-support-materials-in-fff/> [Accessed 25 Apr. 2022].

amount of lactic acid into foods.⁵ This should be harmless in itself, but 3D models made of PLA may contain traces of other materials, such as:

- Brass, steel, nickel or chrome from the printer nozzle.⁶
- Plastic colouring.
- Metallic impurities from manufacture.⁷

Therefore, contact with the mouth can have unpredictable consequences for health, as impacts will depend on the nozzle, supplier, colour and plastic type used. Furthermore, dirt particles can become wedged between layers of printed filament, making models difficult to clean. These can be microscopic and may act as a transmission vector for bacteria, so if you want to play an instrument seriously it is best not to practice intensively on a 3D printed model. Also, you should clean the instrument regularly, and consider attaching a mouthpiece when playing.

Burns from contact with extruder

Most 3D extruders print at over 200°C in order to melt the PLA.⁸ Take care not to touch the nozzle during printing to avoid hand burns. Also, do not touch the base plate during printing, as this will heat up to provide sufficient adhesion to the model.

⁵ Safety assessment of polylactide (PLA) for use as a food-contact polymer. (1995). *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, [online] 33(4), pp.273–283. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/027869159400145E> [Accessed 10 Jun. 2021].

⁶ 3DJake International. (n.d.). 3D Printer Nozzle Guide - Everything about 3D printer nozzles. [online] Available at: <https://www.3djake.com/info/guide/3d-printer-nozzle-guide> [Accessed 25 Apr. 2022].

⁷ Ghosh, K., Ng, S., Iffelsberger, C. and Pumera, M. (2020). Inherent Impurities in Graphene/Polylactic Acid Filament Strongly Influence on the Capacitive Performance of 3D-Printed Electrode. *Chemistry – A European Journal*, 26(67), pp.15746–15753.

⁸ Hay, Z. (2019). Best 3D Printing Temperatures for PLA, PETG, Nylon, TPU. [online] All3DP. Available at: <https://all3dp.com/2/the-best-printing-temperature-for-different-filaments/>.